

УДК 330.562:338(45)47

SEVERAL ASPECTS OF THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY AND BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN

НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ АВТОМОБИЛЬНОГО БИЗНЕСА И ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

© Saidov D.

Urgench State University,
Khorezm, Uzbekistan, dilshod-saidov@mail.ru

© Саидов Д. Р.

Ургенчский государственный университет,
г. Хорезм, Узбекистан, dilshod-saidov@mail.ru

Аннотация. В данной статье рассмотрены некоторые аспекты устойчивого развития автомобильного бизнеса и промышленности в Узбекистане. Анализируются нормативно-правовые основы, адресная целевая инвестиционная программа развития автомобильного бизнеса, основные социально-экономические показатели и результаты деятельности АК «Узавтопром», который является вышестоящим органом и главным координатором отрасли в Узбекистане.

В процессе работы были получены сведения, что год за годом увеличивается количество локализуемых комплектующих деталей, запчастей для легковых, грузовых автомобилей и сельскохозяйственной техники. Кроме того, в 2015 году благодаря 8 проектам по республике в системе АК «Узавтопром» создано 220 новых рабочих мест и освоено более 42 млрд. сумов внутренних инвестиций. За счет прямых иностранных инвестиций осуществлено 6 проектов и освоено более 7 млн. долларов США и создано более 100 новых рабочих мест в системе АК «Узавтопром».

В 2013–2015 годы рост производства грузовых автомобилей и спецтехники составил почти 270 процентов, аккумуляторов — на 126,7 процентов, в то же время производство легковых автомобилей снизилось на 25 процентов, автобусов — на 68 процентов.

Эти данные свидетельствуют о том, что поэтапно изменяется мировая и внутренняя конъюнктура рынка автомобилей, насыщается внутренний рынок автобусов и легковых автомобилей. Повышается внутренний спрос на грузовые автомобили в связи с процветанием гражданского и жилищного строительства в стране, поэтапным обновлением парка грузовых автомобилей на предприятиях, приобретением новых грузовых и спецавтомобилей со стороны субъектов малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства.

Abstract. In this paper looked through several aspects of the sustainable development of the automotive business and industry in Uzbekistan. We analyzed the legal and regulatory framework, directed investment target program for the development of the automotive business, the main socio-economic indicators and the results of the JSC “Uzavtosanoat”, which is the top of the organization and the main coordinator of the sector in Uzbekistan.

In the process, information obtained that year by year, an increasing number of localized sets of component, parts for cars, trucks and agricultural machinery. In addition, in 2015, because of 8 AK “Uzavtosanoat” system projects in the republic created 220 new jobs and spent more than 42 billion soums of domestic investment. As results of 6 foreign direct investment projects assimilated more than 7 million US dollars and created over 100 new jobs in the system of JSC “Uzavtosanoat”.

In 2013–2015 years increased production of trucks and heavy machinery was almost 270 percent, batteries 126.7 percent, in turn decreased the production of passenger cars by 25 per cent, 68 per cent of the buses.

This data indicates that gradual changes in the world and in the internal conditions of vehicles market is saturated domestic market of buses and cars. Increased domestic demand for trucks due to the prosperity of various types of civil and housing construction in the country, a gradual upgrade of Trucks Park in the enterprises, the acquisition of new trucks and special vehicles from the side of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Ключевые слова: автомобильная промышленность, автомобильный бизнес, запасные части, комплектующие детали, легковой автомобиль, грузовой автомобиль, сельскохозяйственная техника, спецавтомобили.

Keywords: automotive industry, automotive business, spare parts, component parts, passenger cars, trucks, agricultural machinery, special vehicles.

In order to implement in Uzbekistan new strategically significant modern state-of-the-art technological investment projects, to modify enterprises, to ensure stable development of economy by updating technologies, to deepen constituent changes, to widen the production of competitive products for inner and external market, like in other spheres of our economy, a number of projects have been carried out in the automobile industry of our country in 2015 and 2016 based on the decrees of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №2264 “Investment program of Uzbekistan in 2015” and № 2458 in 2015 25 December “Investment program of Uzbekistan in 2016”.

Table 1 is showing the information on the power of production and objects in 2015 on the basis of a targeted program of “Uzavtosanoat” JSC. According to it, 8 projects were implemented on the basis of a targeted program in 2015, 42.12 billion of investment funds were obtained and 220 jobs have been created. As a result, in order to ensure the implementation of the above programs and localization projects, “Uzavtosanoat” JSC started to produce the booths of vehicles, cargo vehicles and spare parts, car windows, “Labo” cars, automobile stators, covered copper wires (see Table 1).

Table 1.

CAPACITIES AND FACILITIES PUT INTO PRODUCTION IN 2015 ON THE BASIS OF A TARGETED PROGRAM OF "UZAVTOSANOAT" JSC

№	The initiators of the project and the name of the project	The name of the production	The annual capacity of the projects in thousands	The volume of investment measured in billion	The number of workplaces created
1	2	3	4	5	6
1.	“JV MAN Auto–Uzbekistan” and “UZAVTOTRAYLER” cargo vehicle cockpit assembly and the development of the processes of decentralization of parts	Spare parts and the booths of commercial vehicles	3,0	16,0	50
2.	Owning the production of the details of the trucks that do not require the durability test by “UzKoram” and “UzDongJu”	The spare parts of the cargo trucks	3,0	4,5	5
3.	The application of the car windows and the installation of new thermal processing lines by “Avtooyna”	Car windows	80,0	7,58	50
4.	Owning the production of high–strength panels by “UzKoram” LTC for cars of “GM Uzbekisatn”	the production of high–strength panels	50,0	3,61	10

1	2	3	4	5	6
5.	Modernization of technological equipment of the “Jizzakh Battery Plant” JSC in “Jizzakh” EFZ	Purchase of tools	Purchase of equipments	2,0	—
6.	Launching the production of “Labo” cars in “GM Uzbekistan”	“Labo” car	5,0	5,93	50
7.	Owning the production of stators for cars of “GM Uzbekistan” in “Navoiy” Economically free zone by “IraeAlterneytor” JV	Stators for cars	200,0	2,0	5
8.	The application of the production of covered copper wires for cars by “Irae Cable” joint venture in Navoi EFZ	Covered copper wires	100,0 tons	0,5	50
	TOTAL			42,12	220

Source: [2]

In accordance with the 11th attachment of the decree of the president on November 17, 2014 № 2264 “Investment program for 2015 of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, in 2015, at the expense of direct foreign investments and loans, the following foreign investment and production capacities were utilized (see Table 2).

We can see in the table 2 that in 2015 by foreign direct investments \$7.08 million were invested, as a result “UZAVTOSANOAT” JSC’s enterprises launched 6 directional projects of the investment in various parts for automobiles, the production of components and spare parts and the level of the certification requirements were done for models of cars exported to foreign countries.

Table 2.

THE AMOUNT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENTS BY LOANS AND FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN 2015 ON THE BASIS OF A TARGETED PROGRAM OF “UZAVTOSANOAT”

№	The initiators of the project	The name of the project and duration	The annual power of the project in thousands	Foreign partner, investor	The amount of investment in million US \$
	“UZAVTOSANOAT” JSC				
1.	For Lacetti (Genra) models production of stamps details	2014–2016	50,0	“IS Tech Co., LTD” company (Korea)	50,0
2.	For cars of “GM Uzbekistan” the production of aluminum production equipment	2014–2016	150,0	“INZI MTCO., LTD” company (Korea)	1,5
3.	Producing chasing arrows for the cars of “GM Uzbekistan”	2014–2016	80,0	Company “Chassy Co.. LTD” (Korea)	0,4
4.	The modernization of outdated equipment for “GM Uzbekistan” joint-stock company (Stage 3)	2014–2016	Purchasing equipments	Foreign company	3,0
5.	Reaching the requirements of the Russian Federation’s certification regulations for exported Matiz cars	2014–2016	17,2 thousand cars	Foreign company	0,56
6.	Equipping the cars of “GM Uzbekistan” joint-stock company with the system ERA Glonas	2014–2016	53,2	Foreign company	0,62
	TOTAL				7,08

Source: [2]

Furthermore, in accordance with 12-attachment of president decree in 2014 17 november № PD-2264 "Investment program for 2015 of the Republic of Uzbekistan", in 2015 based on the condition of enterprises implement huge investment projects at the expense of their own capital, "Avtooyna" LLC applied new lines of windows and thermal processing and as a result, 817.8 million of investments were received producing 80 thousand pieces of glass.

In accordance with the decree on February 4, 2014 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan № PD-2120 "Production of finished products, components, equipment, materials and the localization of production in 2014–2016", "Uzavtosanoat" JSC started to produce system a number of regional businesses and organizations directly involved in the field of automotive components and finished products. In particular, "ELHOLDING" LLC and "PANA" LLC which have the capacity of consumer products with the power of 3000 per year and 65,1 percentage of localization rate. Started to produce 3-wheeled cargo and passenger on a motorcycle. "TASHKENT passenger cars repair factory" JSC with annual capacity of 15 units and the localization rate of 40 percent started to produce non-compartment types of train cars, "Andijan Mechanical plant" started to produce semi-train carriages with the rate of about 50 percent and localization capacity of more than 50, "Nurbek White Gold" in the Republic of Karakalpakstan started to produce batteries with about 60% localization rate and the capacity to produce 1,500 units, also in the region of Namangan "Extra primer bat" LLC started to produce batteries with localization rate of about 70 percent and the production capacity of 1,000 units, Ferghana region's "Gas appliance service" LLC started to produce products with localization rate of about 65 percent and a capacity of 15 units designed for compressed natural gas transportation and distribution, production of semi-trailer tanks [3, 1].

Similar to them "Avtosanoat Sepla" LLC under "Uzavtosanoat" JSC started to produce spare parts and raw materials with the degree of localization of about 35 percent and a design capacity of more than 8150 compound and polymer materials. "UzKoram" LLC started to produce more than 2 thousand bumpers with localization rate of 54.3 percent and the capacity of 150 thousand, covers measurement equipment with the localization rate of 62% and annual design capacity of 2.6 thousand wheels CD cases. "Tashkent Mechanical plant" LLC started to produce the left and right of the steering mechanism with localization level of about 100% and the capacity of per 20 thousand, "stamped PRODUCT" LLC started to produce stamped parts for automobiles and "Metis" LLC started to produce various metric tools with localization rate of 35 percent and a project power of 1.5 billion soums, "AUTO PLAST" LLC in Andijan region started to produce spare parts for cars with localization rate of 43% and a capacity of 67 thousand, Namangan region's "Ucharchak" the joint venture company started to produce automobile spare parts with the localization rate of 60% and an annual design capacity of 375 thousand, Samarkand region's "Stekloplastik" LLC started to produce front facings for Isuzu buses with localization rate of 54% and an annual capacity of 300 units. Ferghana region's "Toxirbek Marghilan" LLC started to produce plastic parts for automobiles with the localization rate of 40% and annual capacity of 0.6 billion sums. "Banner Print" LLC in Tashkent started to produce car radiators Bars for Chevrolet and Daewoo Lacetti with the level of localization of 40% and the capacity of the project in accordance with the capacity of 14.1 thousand and 15 thousand units per years consequently with modification code: 95076731-392630 0001. Chevrolet logo modification with localization rate of 65 percent and a capacity of 29 thousand cars. "Banner Print" LLC also produces now the emblem for the Chevrolet Lacetti cars at the front and rear with the localization rate of 65% and an annual capacity of 29 thousand units per year respectively by 14.1 thousand and 15 thousand to 30 thousand units the localization of 60% of the project capacity of 29 thousand units of the Lacetti and to its the back side of the production DAEWOO logos. "Met-Fur-Servis" LLC started to produce pieces of metal equipment with the localization rate of 71% and an annual capacity of 600 million and gofrotubes for 1800 meter long of vehicles [1, 3, 4].

It should be noted that № PD-2120 "Production of finished products, components, equipment and materials and their localization in 2014–2016" On the application of Articles 3, local manufacturers will be recommended to localize components and spare parts, ready to be brought to a list of products in 2016 and most of them were implemented. In particular, the automotive

industry is charging the batteries directly from equipment, fluid pumps, fluid correctors, automobile fuel pumps, multi-stage and single-stage centrifugal, up loader and their parts, cars, trucks, agricultural machinery for metal, rubber and reinforcing parts, electrical areas (lighting, sound, signalization– symbols, window cleaners) parts, radiators, bearings and car CCTVs, Nexia, Matiz, Lacetti, Cobalt, Spark, Damas, Isuzu cars damper ressons, ignition lights, liquid, and gas consumptions, pressure measuring equipment (speedometer– manometers), acoustic systems (columns), sewing car seat upholstery textile materials are used in cars, machinery and vehicles for lubricating material are saved for the localization.

If we speak about the main results of “Uzavtosanoat” JSC in 2013–2015, commercial production worth of 7437.8 billion were produced in 2013, whereas this showed 8896.3 billion soums in 2014. About 1500.0 billion or 119.6 percent and in 2015 it was 7482.4 billion commercial products (see Table 3).

Table 3.

THE MAIN RESULTS OF “UZAVTOSANOAT” JSC IN 2013-2015

<i>Name of the indicators</i>	<i>Measure</i>	2013	2014	2015
The amount of commercial products	Bill. sums	7 437,8	8 896,3	7482,4
The amount of consuming products	Bill. sums	5 725,2	6 073,8	4904,5
The amount of charging services	Bill. sums	32,1	43,5	49,0
The number of staff	Thousand people киши	22,6	25,1	26,2
Occupying funds according investment project	Mil. dollars	108,5	96,9	79,3
The implementation of plans on cooperation stock	Bill. sums	1 666,0	1 865,3	671,7

Source: [5]

Table 4 shows that during 2013–2015 the production of car batteries increased 126.7 percent were in 2013 produced 476.1 thousand units compared to 603.4 thousand units in 2015. In addition, in 2013, 246.6 thousand cars were produced, 185.4 thousand units were produced in 2015.

This means that the instability in the foreign markets and lead to social and political situations in the world and with the saturation of the domestic market, and it is directly related to the production volume of goods sold in the market.

Table 4.

THE MAIN PRODUCTIONAL DYNAMICS OF “UZAVTOSANOAT” JSC IN 2013-2015

<i>Name of the products</i>	<i>Measuring type</i>	2013	2014	2015
Cars	thousands	246,6	245,7	185,4
ISUZU buses	units	2 364	2 588	754
ISUZU trucks	units	1 136	1 217	3056
MAN trucks	units	1 201	1 245	1250
Batteries	thousand	476,1	485	603,4
Power aggregations	thousand	122,9	133,7	87,1

Source: [5]

Table 4 shows information about the main productional dynamics of “Uzavtosanoat” JSC in 2013–2015.

A similar situation may be observed in the production of Isuzu buses, where 2364 units of buses were produced in 2013, but in 2015, only 764 units of Isuzu buses were produced. However, the trends in the growth of production are seen in Isuzu trucks. Because the trucking industry in 2013 produced 1136 trucks, while in 2015 it had 3056 Isuzu trucks.

In a word, this case proves directly that the Isuzu buses are satisfying gradually increasing the intensity of the domestic market of the country, which is one of the objective laws of the market economy based on the demand in the bus applied to the production of goods. In addition, the production of trucks increasing trend of this type of truck models in foreign markets and the width of the race, diversity and the high demand for these types of special equipment and trucks in the domestic market as well as small business and private entrepreneurship, Moreover other organizations and enterprises in the form of property truck fleet are gradually upgrading.

Sources:

1. Ukaz Prezidenta Respubliki Uzbekistan ot 4 marta 2015 goda № UP-4707 «O Programme mer po obespecheniyu strukturnykh preobrazovaniy, modernizatsii i diversifikatsii proizvodstva na 2015–2019 gody». Rezhim dostupa:

http://www.norma.uz/raznoe/ukaz_prezidenta_respubliki_uzbekistan_ot_15_maya_2015_goda (data obrashcheniya 12.12.2016).

2. Postanovleniya Prezidenta Respubliki Uzbekistan № PP-2264 ot 17 noyabrya 2014 goda «Ob investitsionnoi programme Respubliki Uzbekistan na 2015 god» Rezhim dostupa: <https://mineconomy.uz/ru/taxonomy/term/493>. (data obrashcheniya 12.12.2016).

3. Postanovleniya Prezidenta Respubliki Uzbekistan ot 04.02.2014 g. № PP–2120 «O Programme lokalizatsii proizvodstva gotovoi produktsii, komplektuyushchikh izdelii i materialov na 2014–2016 gody» Rezhim dostupa:

http://www.ved.gov.ru/moder_innovac/analytic/analytical_materials/realiz_progr_localiz/ (data obrashcheniya 12.12.2016).

4. Postanovleniya Prezidenta Respubliki Uzbekistan ot 11.02.2015 g. №PP-2298 «O programme lokalizatsii proizvodstva gotovoi produktsii, komplektuyushchikh izdelii i materialov na 2015–2019 gody» Rezhim dostupa:

http://www.norma.uz/novoe_v_zakonodatelstve/novaya_programma_lokalizatsii (data obrashcheniya 12.12.2016).

5. Statistika. Rezhim dostupa: <http://uzavtosanoat.uz/statistika.html>. (data obrashcheniya 12.12.2016).

Источники:

1. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан от 4 марта 2015 года № УП-4707 «О Программе мер по обеспечению структурных преобразований, модернизации и диверсификации производства на 2015–2019 годы». Режим доступа: http://www.norma.uz/raznoe/ukaz_prezidenta_respubliki_uzbekistan_ot_15_maya_2015_goda (дата обращения 12.12.2016).

2. Постановления Президента Республики Узбекистан № ПП-2264 от 17 ноября 2014 года «Об инвестиционной программе Республики Узбекистан на 2015 год» Режим доступа: <https://mineconomy.uz/ru/taxonomy/term/493>. (дата обращения 12.12.2016).

3. Постановления Президента Республики Узбекистан от 04.02.2014 г. № ПП–2120 «О Программе локализации производства готовой продукции, комплектующих изделий и материалов на 2014–2016 годы» Режим доступа:

http://www.ved.gov.ru/moder_innovac/analytic/analytical_materials/realiz_progr_localiz/ (дата обращения 12.12.2016).

4. Постановления Президента Республики Узбекистан от 11.02.2015 г. №ПП-2298 «О программе локализации производства готовой продукции, комплектующих изделий и

материалов на 2015–2019 годы» Режим доступа:

http://www.norma.uz/novoe_v_zakonodatelstve/novaya_programma_lokalizacii (дата обращения 12.12.2016).

5. Статистика. Режим доступа: <http://uzavtosanoat.uz/statistika.html>. (дата обращения 12.12.2016).

*Работа поступила
в редакцию 12.01.2017 г.*

*Принята к публикации
16.01.2017 г.*

Cite as (APA):

Saidov D. (2017) Several aspects of the sustainable Development of automobile industry and business in Uzbekistan. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*. (2), 292–298. Available at: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/saidov-dr>, accessed 15.02.2017.

Ссылка для цитирования:

Сайдов Д. Р. Некоторые аспекты устойчивого развития автомобильного бизнеса и промышленности в Узбекистане // Бюллетень науки и практики. Электрон. журн. 2017. №2 (15). С. 292–298. Режим доступа: <http://www.bulletennauki.com/saidov-dr> (дата обращения 15.02.2017). (На англ.).